

THE ROLE OF BIOLOGICALLY ACTIVE FOOD SUPPLEMENTS IN HUMAN VITALITY

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Relevance: Dietary supplements (DS) are substances that activate the body's self-regulation processes, restoring its natural dynamic balance and paving the way for healing. In the US, 80% of the population uses them, and in Europe, over 50%. Dietary supplements are natural or similar biologically active substances intended for direct oral administration in the form of powder, tablets, capsules, syrups, extracts, tinctures, concentrates, etc.

The goal of our research is to analyze the literature and determine the role of dietary supplements in human life.

Materials and Methods. Our research data consisted of available literature on dietary supplements and their role in supporting the human body. The research method involved analyzing the data presented in the literature. Biologically active food supplements (BAS) are components of natural or naturally occurring biologically active substances intended for direct consumption or inclusion in food products. Their purpose is to enrich the human diet with biologically active substances or their combinations. Dietary supplements are obtained from plant, animal, or mineral sources, as well as by chemical and biotechnological methods. Dietary supplements (DS) added to food occupy a position between medicines and foods. The main difference is that medications are aimed at treating a specific disease, symptom, or pathology, or eliminating its causative agents. Dietary supplements, on the other hand, are aimed at replenishing the deficiency of specific micronutrients.

Results: The analysis showed that dietary supplements (DS) are biologically active substances and their compositions intended for direct consumption with food or inclusion in food products. DS are food products, not drugs. They are used as an additional source of biologically active substances (dietary fiber, vitamins, minerals, amino acids) to replenish their deficiencies and optimize the diet. Dietary supplements, such as biologically active additives, they are contain small amounts of all the necessary plastic and regulatory substances of plant, animal, and mineral origin. They are available in capsules and taken orally. This is the simplest method of administration and is much more pleasant than injections. Moreover, it eliminates overdose, since all substances are contained in organic compounds.

Conclusions: Based on the analysis, it was established that dietary supplements are produced in dosage forms: powders, tablets, capsules, syrups, extracts, tinctures, and concentrates. Their purpose is to enrich the human diet with biologically active substances or their complexes. In other words, dietary supplements (DS) are used not as a primary preventative or therapeutic measure, but only as an adjunct. Furthermore, while medications have a fixed formula, DS are a complex of active ingredients in a random ratio. Thus, biologically active food supplements contain substances necessary to maintain normal vital functions and increase the body's non-specific resistance, and play an important role as additional or auxiliary means of treating various diseases.